

Two-parameter debris-flow simulations using actual-event topography: source-volume and maximum-erosion-depth effects on downstream line-based indicators

Jun Katagiri¹, Hidetaka Saomoto¹, and Takayuki Shinohara¹

¹Integrated Research Center for Resilient Infrastructure, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan

Non-peer-reviewed technical preprint, June 26, 2026

Document type: Non-peer-reviewed technical preprint. This document reports a controlled numerical experiment and has not undergone external peer review.

Abstract

Rainfall-induced debris flows may originate from sediment supplied by upstream slope failures and may entrain additional channel-bed or valley-fill deposits during runout. In post-event surveys and numerical back-analyses, however, the amount of sediment derived from the initial failure and the amount additionally supplied by erosion during runout are difficult to distinguish. This technical preprint documents a controlled two-parameter numerical experiment using topography from an actual debris-flow event and a prescribed rectangular initial failure area. The thickness prescribed within the rectangular initial failure area and the maximum erosion depth along the flow path are systematically varied as control parameters. The aim is not to reproduce the target event using a single optimal parameter set or to establish a general law, but to record how downstream line-based indicators respond to these modelling assumptions in this numerical setup. For each simulation case, the maximum cross-sectional area indicator A_{\max} , the maximum discharge-proxy indicator Q_{\max} , and the flow-depth-weighted mean velocity magnitude at the time of Q_{\max} , denoted as $V_{Q_{\max}}$, are evaluated along a representative downstream cross-line. The 131 valid simulation cases show that A_{\max} and Q_{\max} respond more systematically to maximum erosion depth than to the prescribed thickness within the initial failure area. The velocity indicator $V_{Q_{\max}}$ also shows a stronger association with maximum erosion depth, although its spatial response pattern is more complex. These results are intended as a documented numerical-experiment dataset for discussing how assumptions about source volume and erosion potential can affect downstream debris-flow indicators.

1 Introduction

Rainfall-induced debris flows in mountain catchments have caused severe loss of life and infrastructure damage in many parts of the world [Iverson, 1997, Takahashi, 2007, Jakob and Hungr, 2005]. Landslide-related hazards include various types of mass movements, such as debris flows, landslides, and rapid shallow slope failures, and their triggering mechanisms and damage characteristics differ substantially [Hungr et al., 2014]. Among these hazards, debris flows are particularly dangerous because they can travel rapidly along steep channels as mixtures of sediment and water. The time between initiation in the upstream catchment and arrival in downstream areas can therefore be very short. As a result, ensuring the safety of residents may be difficult if evacuation starts only after the event has occurred. It is therefore important to identify catchments prone to debris-flow initiation and runout and to consider appropriate combinations of structural countermeasures, such as sabo dams or check dams, land-use management, and warning and

evacuation planning [Osanai et al., 2010].

In catchments where debris flows have occurred repeatedly, especially where recent disaster records are available, information on source areas, flow paths, deposition zones, and affected areas has often been accumulated through post-event survey reports, academic papers, and administrative documents. In Japan, spatial information related to sediment-related hazard areas and potential sediment-disaster sites has been compiled and released as GIS datasets by national and local governmental agencies [Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism of Japan, 2022, 2010]. For the 2021 debris-flow disaster in the Izusan district of Atami City, Shizuoka Prefecture, which is used as the target area in this study, several reports, survey results, and topographic datasets have also been made publicly available by governmental agencies, academic societies, and research groups [Shizuoka Prefecture, 2022, Atami City Council Special Investigation Committee on the Izusan Debris Flow Disaster, 2023, Kitamura and Ikeda, 2021, Imaizumi et al., 2022, Sasaki et al., 2021, Zhang et al., 2022]. Such post-event

datasets provide important baseline information for identifying source conditions, flow paths, deposition areas, and affected areas. They are also useful for discussing downstream land-use planning, evacuation-site planning, infrastructure management, and possible structural countermeasures.

Information recorded in post-event surveys commonly includes runout or inundation areas, erosion zones, and deposition areas. However, the spatial patterns observed in a past event represent only one outcome that occurred under a specific combination of rainfall conditions, ground conditions, source conditions, and erosion conditions. In future rainfall events, the initial landslide volume and the amount of sediment entrained during runout may vary depending on rainfall amount, rainfall intensity, antecedent rainfall, groundwater conditions, and possible weakening of slope or channel-bed materials due to earthquakes or other disturbances. Therefore, directly using the affected area of a past event as the expected impact area of a future event may lead to an underestimation or overestimation of downstream hazards. Evaluating how uncertainties in the initial landslide volume and erosion or entrainment conditions affect downstream debris-flow indicators is therefore important for debris-flow hazard assessment and disaster-risk reduction planning [Baggio et al., 2024].

One of the key controls on downstream debris-flow response is the volume of sediment initially supplied from the upstream source area. The initial landslide volume is expected to depend on rainfall and ground conditions, but determining a unique value for this volume in real events is difficult. In addition, the extent to which channel-bed or valley-fill deposits are eroded and entrained during flow propagation can strongly influence flow depth, discharge, runout extent, and deposition patterns [Berger et al., 2011, Frank et al., 2015]. However, in post-event surveys, it is difficult to independently determine which part of the sediment originated from the initial failure and which part was additionally supplied by erosion during runout. Furthermore, substantial uncertainty remains in representing the erodibility of channel-bed or valley-fill deposits using a single physical parameter.

To evaluate such uncertainties systematically, the initial landslide volume and erosion conditions must be controlled independently so that their effects on downstream responses can be compared. However, reproducing an entire real catchment in physical experiments, generating initial failures with prescribed locations and volumes, and controlling erosion conditions along the whole flow path are difficult. Therefore, in this study, we construct a numerical model using topography from an actual debris-flow event, define a prescribed rectangular initial failure area, and conduct a two-parameter numerical experiment in which the thickness of the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth are systematically varied.

The objective of this technical preprint is not to reproduce a specific debris-flow event with a single optimal parameter set or to establish a general predic-

tive law. Instead, it documents a controlled numerical experiment using actual-event topography to evaluate how two uncertain modelling assumptions, namely the initial landslide volume and maximum erosion depth, are reflected in downstream line-based debris-flow indicators. Specifically, we evaluate three line-based indicators along a representative downstream cross-line: the maximum cross-sectional area indicator A_{\max} , the maximum discharge-proxy indicator Q_{\max} , and the flow-depth-weighted mean velocity magnitude at the time of Q_{\max} , denoted as $V_{Q_{\max}}$. Through these comparisons, we examine the sensitivity of downstream responses to changes in source and erosion conditions. This study clarifies how assumptions regarding initial landslide volume and erosion potential can influence the interpretation of debris-flow hazard assessments based on post-event disaster data.

2 Numerical experiment design using actual event topography

In this study, we used the topography of a catchment affected by the 2021 debris-flow disaster in Atami City, Shizuoka Prefecture, Japan, as an example of actual-event terrain. Numerical experiments were conducted to evaluate how the initial landslide volume and maximum erosion depth influence downstream line-based debris-flow indicators. The target catchment is a case in which a rainfall-induced debris flow occurred and for which post-event survey reports, topographic data, and information on the failure source area are publicly available. In this study, this case is not used to reproduce the specific event in detail. Instead, it is used as a numerical testbed that includes an actual flow path, valley topography, and downstream deposition area. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as a sensitivity analysis using actual-event topography, rather than as an evaluation of the reproducibility of the target event.

In the simulations, the initial landslide volume and maximum erosion depth were defined as the two primary control parameters. These parameters were varied to represent changes in the amount of sediment initially supplied from the rectangular initial failure area and the amount of sediment that could be additionally entrained from channel-bed or valley-fill deposits during runout. Other computational conditions were kept common among the simulation cases. We then compared changes in downstream line-based indicators evaluated along a representative cross-line. This experimental design allowed us to evaluate how uncertainties in source and erosion conditions are reflected in downstream debris-flow intensity.

2.1 Target topography and initial sediment-supply area

A digital elevation model of a mountain catchment affected by an actual debris-flow event was used as the target topography. In this catchment, sediment was

Figure 1: Computational domain and parameter-setting framework used in this study. The background image shows the actual-event topography and surrounding land use, overlaid with elevation information. The black mesh indicates the computational domain, the grey rectangle in the upstream area indicates the prescribed rectangular initial failure area (approximately 4610.6 m^2), and the downstream black line indicates the cross-line used to evaluate the debris-flow indicators. The domain width is 265 m, the curved channel length is approximately 1905 m, and the grid size is 4.9 m.

supplied by a slope failure in the upstream area, and the mobilized material travelled downstream along the valley topography. By using this actual terrain, the numerical experiments incorporated topographic factors that are difficult to represent using simplified idealized channels, such as variations in valley width, slope gradient, channel curvature, and downstream topographic constraints.

The computational domain was defined to include the prescribed rectangular initial failure area, the main flow path, and the downstream area where deposition or inundation could occur (Fig. 1). The computational domain had a width of 265 m and followed a curved channel length of approximately 1905 m. The grid size was 4.9 m. The topographic data were based on a 5 m resolution digital elevation model provided by the Geospatial Information Authority of Japan.

A rectangular initial failure area was defined in the upstream part of the computational domain with reference to post-event survey reports and publicly available information [Shizuoka Prefecture, 2022, Atami City Council Special Investigation Committee on the Izusan Debris Flow Disaster, 2023, Sasaki et al., 2021, Zhang et al., 2022]. This rectangular area was defined with reference to the location and approximate extent of the actual failure, but it was not intended to reproduce the exact failure shape. The area of the prescribed rectangle was approximately 4610.6 m^2 . In this study, this rectangular initial failure area was used as a com-

mon source-area setting for all simulation cases, and the initial landslide volume was controlled by systematically varying the thickness prescribed within this area.

2.2 Numerical model

Debris-flow runout was simulated using a two-dimensional numerical model that represents sediment-water mixtures flowing over topography and the associated erosion and deposition processes. The model computes variables such as flow depth, flow velocity, sediment concentration, and bed elevation change on a computational grid. In this framework, sediment supplied from the rectangular initial failure area can become mobilized and travel downstream along the valley.

The numerical model used in this study accounts for debris-flow motion, flow resistance, sediment transport, and erosion-deposition processes. When the flow erodes channel-bed or valley-fill deposits during runout, the eroded sediment is added to the moving mixture. Conversely, where the transport capacity of the flow decreases, sediment deposition occurs and the bed elevation changes. In this manner, the simulations account not only for the sediment initially supplied from the rectangular initial failure area but also for sediment entrained during downstream propagation.

The model requires input parameters related to flow

resistance, sediment concentration, erosion and deposition, time stepping, and boundary conditions. In this study, these parameters were not calibrated to reproduce the target event with a single optimal parameter set. Instead, they were fixed at common values for all simulation cases. The main computational conditions and model parameters are summarized in Table 2. This setup allowed the differences among simulation results to be interpreted primarily in terms of differences in the initial landslide volume and maximum erosion depth.

2.3 Initial landslide volume and maximum erosion depth

The initial landslide volume was prescribed by varying the thickness assigned within the rectangular initial failure area. The spatial extent of this rectangular source area was kept the same in all simulation cases, and only the thickness prescribed within the area was varied. This setting produced multiple simulation cases with the same topography and source location but different amounts of initially supplied sediment.

The initial landslide volume may vary depending on rainfall amount, rainfall intensity, antecedent rainfall, groundwater conditions, and ground properties. In this study, these complex initiation mechanisms were not modelled explicitly. Instead, the initial landslide volume was treated as a control parameter representing uncertainty in the amount of sediment supplied from the rectangular initial failure area. Therefore, the initial landslide volume in each simulation case should be interpreted as a scenario representing possible differences in source conditions, rather than as a value uniquely derived from a specific rainfall condition.

The maximum erosion depth was defined as a parameter representing the upper limit of sediment that could be additionally entrained from channel-bed or valley-fill deposits along the flow path. During runout, debris flows may erode channel deposits and valley-fill materials, thereby changing discharge, sediment concentration, flow depth, runout extent, and deposition patterns. Therefore, erosion and entrainment during flow propagation can substantially influence downstream responses.

However, in real debris-flow events, it is difficult to uniquely evaluate the erodibility of the entire flow path. Factors such as grain-size distribution, density, water content, degree of compaction, vegetation, and local topography can affect the susceptibility of channel-bed and valley-fill materials to erosion. Measuring these properties over an entire catchment and representing them using a single physical parameter is generally impractical. Therefore, in this study, maximum erosion depth was treated as a lumped proxy for the potential entrainment of sediment during runout.

The prescribed thickness of the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth were combined to construct a two-dimensional parameter space. The thickness prescribed within the initial failure area was varied from 1 to 23 m at 2 m intervals, and the maximum

erosion depth was varied from 0.75 to 5.75 m at 0.5 m intervals. This resulted in 12 values for the prescribed thickness and 11 values for the maximum erosion depth, giving a total of 132 attempted simulation cases. One case in which the automated parameter-sweep workflow did not complete properly was excluded from the analysis. The results and correlation analyses in Sect. 3 are therefore based on the remaining 131 valid cases. The parameter-sweep design is summarized in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 2.

2.4 Definition of line-based downstream indicators

For each simulation case, debris-flow indicators were evaluated along a representative cross-line located in the downstream area. Because important infrastructure is located downstream of the target catchment, the analysis line was placed immediately upstream of this infrastructure. However, the purpose of this study is not to estimate the actual force acting on a specific structure. Rather, the line-based indicators were used to compare the scale, transport intensity, and representative velocity of debris-flow material reaching the downstream area among simulation cases.

Let s denote the coordinate along the analysis line, t denote time, $h(s, t)$ denote flow depth, and $v(s, t)$ denote the magnitude of the depth-averaged velocity vector exported by the numerical model. First, the cross-sectional area indicator $A(t)$, which represents the scale of flowing material present on the analysis line, was defined as

$$A(t) = \int_L h(s, t) ds, \quad (1)$$

where L denotes the analysis line. The unit of $A(t)$ is m^2 .

Second, a discharge-proxy indicator $Q(t)$ was defined as

$$Q(t) = \int_L h(s, t)v(s, t) ds. \quad (2)$$

Here, $v(s, t)$ is the magnitude of the velocity vector at each point on the analysis line. The dimensional unit of $Q(t)$ is therefore $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$. However, because the calculation uses velocity magnitude rather than the line-normal velocity component, $Q(t)$ should not be interpreted as an exact physical discharge through the line. Instead, it is used here as a discharge-proxy indicator for comparing the transport intensity of material reaching the downstream area among simulation cases.

Third, to examine the velocity contribution separately from the flow scale, we defined the representative velocity magnitude at the time of maximum $Q(t)$ as

$$V_{Q_{\max}} = \frac{Q(t_{Q_{\max}})}{A(t_{Q_{\max}})}, \quad (3)$$

where $t_{Q_{\max}}$ denotes the time at which $Q(t)$ reaches its maximum. This quantity represents the flow-depth-weighted mean velocity magnitude along the analysis

Table 1: Design of the two-parameter sweep.

Parameter	Range	Increment	Number of values
Thickness of the initial failure area	1–23	2	12
Maximum erosion depth	0.75–5.75	0.5	11
Attempted simulation cases	–	–	132
Valid cases used in analysis	–	–	131

Figure 2: Two-parameter sweep design used in this study. Black points indicate the 131 valid simulation cases used in the analysis. The cross indicates the excluded grid point corresponding to the one attempted case for which the automated parameter-sweep workflow did not complete properly.

line at the time of maximum transport intensity. It is not a line-normal velocity; rather, it is a representative velocity magnitude of the flowing material on the analysis line.

For each simulation case, time series of $A(t)$, $Q(t)$, and $Q(t)/A(t)$ were calculated from the exported line data. The maximum cross-sectional area indicator A_{\max} , the maximum discharge-proxy indicator Q_{\max} , and the velocity indicator $V_{Q_{\max}}$ were then used as the main downstream indicators. These indicators were used to evaluate how changes in the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth affect downstream debris-flow intensity.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Overall trends in the simulation results

Figure 3 shows the three downstream indicators shown over the two-dimensional parameter space defined by the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth. The analysis in this section is based on the 131 valid cases shown in Fig. 2. One attempted case in which the automated parameter-sweep workflow did not complete properly was excluded from the analysis.

Overall, A_{\max} and Q_{\max} were much more sensitive to maximum erosion depth than to the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area. As

the maximum erosion depth increased, both the cross-sectional scale and transport intensity of the flowing material reaching the downstream representative cross-line increased consistently. In contrast, variations along the prescribed-thickness direction were comparatively small, and increasing the thickness of the initial failure area did not necessarily lead to a monotonic increase in A_{\max} or Q_{\max} .

By contrast, $V_{Q_{\max}}$ responded differently from A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . Although $V_{Q_{\max}}$ also tended to increase with maximum erosion depth, its spatial pattern in the parameter space was more complex than those of A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . This suggests that the effect of maximum erosion depth appeared primarily as an increase in the amount of flowing material passing through the downstream cross-line, rather than as a uniform increase in representative velocity.

3.2 Effects of maximum erosion depth on downstream flow scale and transport intensity

A_{\max} and Q_{\max} showed very similar responses to increasing maximum erosion depth. When the maximum erosion depth was small, only a limited amount of flowing material reached the downstream cross-line. In contrast, when the maximum erosion depth was large, A_{\max} and Q_{\max} increased substantially even for the same the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area.

This result indicates that erosion and entrainment

Figure 3: Parameter-space maps of downstream line-based indicators for the 131 valid simulation cases: (a) maximum cross-sectional area indicator A_{\max} , (b) maximum discharge-proxy indicator Q_{\max} , and (c) flow-depth-weighted mean velocity magnitude at the time of Q_{\max} , $V_{Q_{\max}}$. The horizontal axis represents the thickness prescribed within the rectangular initial failure area, and the vertical axis represents the maximum erosion depth along the flow path. Colour fields were smoothed for visualization, and black dots indicate the original valid simulation cases. The cross marks the excluded grid point corresponding to the one attempted case for which the automated parameter-sweep workflow did not complete properly.

Table 2: Simulation parameters used in the debris-flow simulations.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Simulation time	100	s
Time step	0.004	s
Density of water	1000	kg m ⁻³
Density of sediment	2650	kg m ⁻³
Static sediment concentration	0.6	–
Fraction of sediment behaving as fluid	0.2	–
Minimum flow depth	0.01	m
Internal friction angle	34	deg
Laminar-layer thickness	constant	–
Ratio of laminar-layer thickness	0.4	–
Resistance coefficient	72	–
Bed material type	uniform sand	–
Mean grain size	0.01	m

potential during runout can substantially alter the amount of flowing material reaching the downstream area. In particular, the close similarity between the parameter-space patterns of A_{\max} and Q_{\max} suggests that, under the present modelling conditions, the increase in transport intensity was mainly associated with an increase in cross-sectional flow scale. In other words, increasing maximum erosion depth appears to have increased sediment entrainment during runout and, consequently, the amount of flowing material passing through the downstream cross-line, rather than simply increasing flow velocity.

To quantify these tendencies, we evaluated the relationships between each control parameter and the downstream indicators using Pearson’s correlation coefficient, Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient, and Chatterjee’s correlation coefficient ξ . Pearson’s coefficient was used to evaluate linear association, and Spearman’s coefficient was used to evaluate monotonic rank association. Chatterjee’s coefficient was used as a supplementary measure of dependence that is not restricted to monotonic relationships [Chatterjee, 2021]. Because the parameter-sweep dataset has a discrete grid structure and includes many tied values of the thickness of the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth, the absolute values of Chatterjee’s coefficient may be affected by the treatment of ties. Therefore, Chatterjee’s coefficient was interpreted as a supplementary measure alongside Pearson’s and Spearman’s coefficients.

Table 3 summarizes the correlation coefficients for the 131 valid cases. For A_{\max} , the Pearson, Spearman, and Chatterjee coefficients with maximum erosion depth were 0.983, 0.990, and 0.955, respectively. In contrast, the corresponding coefficients with the thickness of the initial failure area were 0.114, 0.110, and 0.529. Similar results were obtained for Q_{\max} : the coefficients with maximum erosion depth were also high, at 0.964, 0.988, and 0.953, whereas those with thickness of the initial failure area were 0.137, 0.118, and 0.534.

These results indicate that maximum erosion depth had a much stronger and more systematic association with A_{\max} and Q_{\max} than did the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area. The weak Pearson and Spearman correlations with the thickness of the initial failure area show that increasing the thickness of the initial failure area did not lead to a simple linear or monotonic increase in downstream flow scale or transport intensity. The moderate Chatterjee coefficients for the thickness of the initial failure area suggest that non-monotonic or local dependence may still remain. However, all three correlation measures show that the association with maximum erosion depth was much stronger than that with the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area.

3.3 Response of the representative velocity $V_{Q_{\max}}$

$V_{Q_{\max}}$ showed a more complex response than A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . The Pearson, Spearman, and Chatterjee coefficients between $V_{Q_{\max}}$ and maximum erosion depth were 0.826, 0.857, and 0.846, respectively, and were clearly higher than the corresponding coefficients for the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area. Thus, the representative velocity was also clearly associated with maximum erosion depth.

However, the parameter-space map of $V_{Q_{\max}}$ did not show the simple vertical increase pattern observed for A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . This is likely because velocity responses are influenced not only by maximum erosion depth but also by channel geometry, local slope, flow depth, deposition, and deceleration processes. In particular, $V_{Q_{\max}}$ represents the velocity at the time when $Q(t)$ reaches its maximum, and the conditions that maximize the amount of flowing material do not necessarily coincide with those that maximize velocity.

This result is important for interpreting the role of maximum erosion depth. If maximum erosion depth uniformly increased flow velocity, $V_{Q_{\max}}$ would be expected to show a pattern as simple and consistent

Table 3: Correlation coefficients between control parameters and downstream line-based indicators for the 131 valid cases.

Indicator	Control parameter	Pearson's r	Spearman's ρ	Chatterjee's ξ
A_{\max}	Thickness of the initial failure area	0.114	0.110	0.529
A_{\max}	Maximum erosion depth	0.983	0.990	0.955
Q_{\max}	Thickness of the initial failure area	0.137	0.118	0.534
Q_{\max}	Maximum erosion depth	0.964	0.988	0.953
$V_{Q_{\max}}$	Thickness of the initial failure area	0.138	0.175	0.545
$V_{Q_{\max}}$	Maximum erosion depth	0.826	0.857	0.846

as those of A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . Instead, $V_{Q_{\max}}$ showed a more complex response. Therefore, the increase in Q_{\max} observed in this study is interpreted as being more strongly associated with an increase in the amount of flowing material passing through the downstream cross-line than with a uniform increase in representative velocity.

3.4 Limited influence of the thickness of the initial failure area

Increasing the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area was not entirely without effect on the downstream indicators. The Chatterjee coefficients indicate moderate dependence between the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area and each indicator, suggesting that this parameter may have some influence on downstream responses.

However, both Pearson and Spearman coefficients were low, and no clear linear or monotonic relationship was identified between the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area and A_{\max} , Q_{\max} , or $V_{Q_{\max}}$. As shown in Fig. 3, variations along the prescribed-thickness direction were much smaller than those along the maximum erosion depth direction. Therefore, the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area may modify downstream responses in a secondary manner, but it was not the primary controlling factor for the downstream line-based indicators considered in this study.

Several mechanisms may explain this response. First, once a sufficient amount of initial sediment is supplied, the scale of material reaching the downstream area may become more strongly controlled by erosion and entrainment along the flow path than by the initial supply itself. Second, excessive initial sediment supply may promote deposition or changes in flow configuration in the upstream or middle reaches, and may not directly increase flow scale or representative velocity at the downstream cross-line. Third, topographic constraints specific to the target catchment, such as changes in valley width, slope gradient, and channel curvature, may have reduced the influence of source volume on the downstream response.

However, the present analysis is based on indicators evaluated at a downstream representative cross-line and does not directly quantify the sediment budget over the entire catchment. Therefore, the reason for

the limited influence of the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area cannot be rigorously explained in terms of total erosion volume, total deposition volume, or reach-scale sediment balance. What can be concluded from the present data is that, for the line-based downstream indicators considered here, the influence of maximum erosion depth was consistently larger than that of the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area.

3.5 Implications for debris-flow hazard assessment

The results of this study highlight the importance of evaluating erosion and entrainment potential during runout, in addition to the initial landslide volume, in debris-flow hazard assessment. In post-event back-analyses and hazard assessments, considerable attention is often paid to the estimation of initial landslide volume. However, in the present simulations, maximum erosion depth was more strongly reflected in downstream flow scale and transport intensity than the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area.

The strong dependence of both A_{\max} and Q_{\max} on maximum erosion depth indicates that additional sediment supply during runout can substantially change the scale of debris flow reaching downstream areas. At the same time, the more complex response of $V_{Q_{\max}}$ suggests that representative velocity is more strongly affected by topographic and flow-state factors than the scale-related indicators are. Therefore, the dominant effect of maximum erosion depth should be interpreted primarily as an increase in the amount of flowing material passing through the downstream cross-line, rather than as a simple increase in flow velocity.

This result indicates that caution is required when downstream debris-flow impacts are estimated solely from the initial landslide volume inferred for a past event. If thick channel-bed deposits or easily erodible valley-fill materials are present along the flow path, downstream flow scale and transport intensity may vary substantially even when the initial landslide volume is similar.

3.6 Limitations of interpretation

The results of this study show that maximum erosion depth strongly affected the downstream line-based in-

dicators. However, this does not imply that maximum erosion depth always dominates debris-flow hazards. The maximum erosion depth used in this study is a lumped proxy for the erodibility or entrainment potential of channel-bed and valley-fill deposits, not a direct geotechnical material parameter. In addition, the rectangular initial failure area, topography, flow-resistance parameters, and boundary conditions were fixed across all simulation cases.

Furthermore, this study did not perform a catchment-scale sediment-budget analysis using cumulative erosion volume, cumulative deposition volume, or sediment outflow from the computational domain. Therefore, to rigorously quantify why maximum erosion depth strongly affected the downstream indicators in terms of total sediment entrainment during runout, additional analyses are required in which domain-wide indicators are output over the entire computational domain and re-evaluated.

Pearson, Spearman, and Chatterjee correlation coefficients describe statistical associations between the control parameters and downstream indicators. They do not directly prove physical causality. Therefore, these correlation coefficients should be interpreted as quantitative evidence that maximum erosion depth was strongly associated with downstream indicators, rather than as a standalone explanation of the detailed physical mechanisms of erosion and entrainment.

The results of this study should therefore be interpreted not as a deterministic hazard assessment for a specific catchment but as a sensitivity analysis showing how uncertainties in source and erosion conditions can appear in downstream indicators in a controlled numerical experiment using actual-event topography. Within this interpretation, the results indicate that debris-flow hazard assessments for downstream areas should explicitly consider not only the initial landslide volume but also the potential for erosion and entrainment along the flow path.

4 Conclusions

This technical preprint documented a two-parameter numerical experiment using topography from an actual debris-flow event in a mountain catchment and a prescribed rectangular initial failure area. The thickness prescribed within the initial failure area and maximum erosion depth were systematically varied to evaluate how two uncertain control factors, namely the initial landslide volume and erosion or entrainment potential during runout, are reflected in downstream debris-flow indicators. The objective of this study was not to reproduce a specific debris-flow event using a single optimal parameter set, but to use an actual event topography as a controlled numerical testbed for sensitivity analysis.

Three line-based indicators were evaluated along a representative downstream cross-line: the maximum cross-sectional area indicator A_{\max} , the maximum discharge-proxy indicator Q_{\max} , and the flow-depth-

weighted mean velocity magnitude at the time of Q_{\max} , denoted as $V_{Q_{\max}}$. One case in which the automated parameter-sweep workflow did not complete properly was excluded from the analysis, and the remaining 131 cases were evaluated. The results showed that A_{\max} and Q_{\max} were much more sensitive to maximum erosion depth than to the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area. Pearson, Spearman, and Chatterjee correlation coefficients also showed strong associations between these two indicators and maximum erosion depth. In contrast, the linear and monotonic associations with the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area were weak, indicating that increasing this thickness did not simply increase downstream flow scale or transport intensity.

The representative velocity $V_{Q_{\max}}$ was also more strongly associated with maximum erosion depth than with the prescribed thickness of the initial failure area. However, its spatial pattern in the parameter space was more complex than those of A_{\max} and Q_{\max} . This result suggests that the influence of maximum erosion depth appeared mainly as an increase in the amount of flowing material passing through the downstream representative cross-line, rather than as a uniform increase in flow velocity. Under the modelling conditions considered in this study, downstream flow scale and transport intensity were therefore strongly influenced not only by the amount of sediment initially supplied from the rectangular initial failure area but also by the potential for sediment erosion and entrainment along the flow path.

These findings indicate that caution is required when debris-flow hazard assessments based on past events focus mainly on estimated initial landslide volume. In post-event investigations, it is difficult to independently determine the amount of sediment derived from the initial failure and the amount additionally supplied by erosion during runout. It is also difficult to evaluate uniquely the erodibility of channel-bed or valley-fill deposits over an entire catchment. The present results show that assumptions regarding erosion and entrainment potential can strongly influence the estimated downstream flow scale and transport intensity.

Several limitations should be noted. First, the maximum erosion depth used in this study is a lumped proxy for the erosion or entrainment potential of channel-bed and valley-fill deposits. It does not directly represent a specific geotechnical parameter or measured material property. Second, this study did not perform a catchment-scale sediment-budget analysis using cumulative erosion volume, cumulative deposition volume, or sediment outflow from the computational domain. Therefore, to rigorously quantify why maximum erosion depth strongly affected the downstream indicators in terms of total entrained sediment volume, additional analyses are required in which domain-wide indicators are output over the entire computational domain and re-evaluated. Third, the indicators used in this study were evaluated along a representative downstream cross-line and do not directly represent the full spatial distribution of debris-flow

hazards over the entire catchment.

The results should therefore be interpreted not as a deterministic hazard assessment for a specific catchment but as a documented controlled numerical experiment using actual-event topography. Within this scope, the results show how uncertainties in initial sediment supply and erosion or entrainment potential can appear in downstream debris-flow indicators in this numerical setup. Future work should include sediment-budget analyses based on cumulative erosion and deposition volumes, comparisons among multiple catchments, parameter settings that account for spatial variations in erodibility, and the introduction of more direct indicators related to line-normal discharge and structural impact forces. Such extensions would help incorporate uncertainties in source and erosion conditions more explicitly into debris-flow hazard assessments based on post-event disaster data.

Code and data availability

The topographic dataset used in this study is available from the Center for Spatial Information Science, The University of Tokyo, as cited in the References. The iRIC software and Morpho2DH solver are available from the iRIC project website. The simulation-derived line-indicator dataset, parameter-sweep settings, and scripts used to aggregate the exported line data and generate the figures are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request, after removal of environment-specific file paths and dependencies.

Author contribution

Jun Katagiri designed the study, performed the numerical simulations and parameter-sweep analyses, processed the exported line data, prepared the figures, and wrote the manuscript.

Competing interests

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

References

Atami City Council Special Investigation Committee on the Izusan Debris Flow Disaster. Investigation report on the izusan debris flow disaster. Technical report, Atami City, February 2023. URL https://www.city.atami.lg.jp/_res/projects/default_project/_page/_001/013/623/R5.2_hokokusho.pdf. in Japanese.

Tommaso Baggio, Marco Martini, Francesco Bettella, and Vincenzo D'Agostino. Debris flow and debris flood hazard assessment in mountain catchments. *CATENA*, 245:108338, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.catena.2024.108338.

Christine Berger, Brian W. McArdell, and Fritz Schlunegger. Direct measurement of channel erosion by debris flows, illgraben, switzerland. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 116(F1): F01002, 2011. doi: 10.1029/2010JF001722.

Sourav Chatterjee. A new coefficient of correlation. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 116(536):2009–2022, 2021. doi: 10.1080/01621459.2020.1758115.

Florian Frank, Brian W. McArdell, Christian Huggel, and Andreas Vieli. The importance of entrainment and bulking on debris flow runout modeling: examples from the swiss alps. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 15:2569–2583, 2015. doi: 10.5194/nhess-15-2569-2015.

Oldrich Hungr, Serge Leroueil, and Luciano Picarelli. The varnes classification of landslide types, an update. *Landslides*, 11:167–194, 2014. doi: 10.1007/s10346-013-0436-y.

Fumitoshi Imaizumi, Nobutomo Osanai, Shinyu Kato, Masaru Koike, Ken'ichirou Kosugi, Yusuke Sakai, Hiroshi Sakaguchi, Yoshifumi Satofuka, Shoki Takayama, Takafumi Tanaka, and Yotaro Nishi. Debris flow disaster in atami, japan, in july 2021. *International Journal of Erosion Control Engineering*, 15(1):1–6, 2022. doi: 10.13101/ijece.15.1.

R. M. Iverson. The physics of debris flows. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 35(3):245–296, 1997.

Matthias Jakob and Oldrich Hungr, editors. *Debris-flow Hazards and Related Phenomena*. Springer Praxis Books. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2005. ISBN 978-3-540-20726-9. doi: 10.1007/b138657.

Akihisa Kitamura and Masayuki Ikeda. A flash report on the debris flow that occurred in the izusan district of atami city, shizuoka prefecture on july 3, 2021. *Geoscience Reports of Shizuoka University*, 48:63–71, 2021. doi: 10.51053/shizuoka.48.0_63. in Japanese.

Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism of Japan. National land numerical information: Sediment disaster hazard areas data (a26). <https://nlftp.mlit.go.jp/ksj/gml/datalist/KsjTmplt-A26.html>, 2010. Dataset; in Japanese; accessed 27 May 2026.

Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism of Japan. National land numerical information: Sediment disaster alert areas data (a33). <https://nlftp.mlit.go.jp/ksj/gml/datalist/KsjTmplt-A33.html>, 2022. Dataset; in Japanese; accessed 27 May 2026.

Nobutomo Osanai, Hideaki Mizuno, and Takahisa Mizuyama. Design standard of control structures against debris flow in japan. *Journal of Disaster Research*, 5(3):307–314, 2010. doi: 10.20965/jdr.2010.p0307.

Reiki Sasaki, Takahiro Shimono, and Noriko Kishimoto. Laser measurement and calculation of elevation changes in the debris-flow source area in atami city before and after the disaster. *Journal of the Japan Society of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 60(6):332–335, 2021. doi: 10.4287/jsprs.60.332. in Japanese.

Shizuoka Prefecture. Report on investigation of the causes of the aizome river debris flow. Technical report, Shizuoka Prefecture, September 2022. URL https://www.pref.shizuoka.jp/_res/projects/default_project/_page_/001/043/591/01index2.pdf. in Japanese.

T. Takahashi. *Debris Flow: Mechanics, Prediction and Countermeasures*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2007.

Shuai Zhang, Fawu Wang, and Ran Li. First insight into the catastrophic atami debris flow induced by a rain gush on 3 july 2021 in shizuoka, japan. *Landslides*, 19:527–532, 2022. doi: 10.1007/s10346-021-01788-1.